

**ETHICS OF EMPLOYEES IN HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM
INDUSTRY**

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Abstract It is a multifunctional study based on an extensive literature review on development, innovation and terrestrial innovation modes. Based on the prime conceptual findings, the model of regional innovation systems is considered to be the most adequate for the tourism system, and the ethics as important structures for its operationalization. Innovation improves organizational productivity and provides a competitive advantage. However, the implementation of new technology may have a negative effect on employees' health, which has received a limited attention in the literature. This exploratory study, based on documentary analysis, in-depth interview and observation, examines the effect of the implementation of Banner (a new administrative and information system) at a higher education institution on employees' mental health.

Ethical behavior is one of the most important requested skills in hospitality. It starts from dress codes, ends on mobilized skills from an employee. Any employee since they start their career in hotel industry they have to follow rules below:

Key: Quality, Skills, Hygiene, Responsibility, Rules, Loyalty, Society, strategies, analyze

Introduction

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conceptual findings, the model of regional innovation systems are considered to be the most adequate for the tourism system and the ethics as important structures for its operationalization. All industry practitioners know the hospitality ethics model as a necessary code of hospitality management that highlights the related morals and principles of this tourism business. So, hospitality ethics refers to the manager's role, employee, hotel, motel or any facility as philosophical ways of treating the business's guests and giving them the best image of working culture, relationship and standards'.

Regarding this theoretical approach, a steppingstone for the analysis of hospitality management systems may be developed, allowing a number of theories to be advanced and checked through the analysis of the results from the empirical part of the thesis.

operation of tourism firms and districts, the networking approaches developed due to the innovation processes, the role of regional knowledge and regional specific conditions for tourism innovation and the perception of tourism enterprises regarding the innovation environment and the benefit of the evolution and success of hospitality ethics.

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Literature review:

Frechtling and Boo (2012) state that generally applied operational principles should provide an assurance to decision makers on particular business decisions taken in accordance to defined rules and regulations of the practice. Majority of organizations do fail to achieve their maximum potential due to scouring implications of poor ethics.

Though some managers indicate that indeed they appreciate the critically of employing professional ethics, Hudson (2007) indicates that majority of them are indeed unsure of the extent to which they should apply it.

According to Kim and Miller (2008), tourism and hospitality industry is one of the most crucial industries that perhaps require observance of the highest possible levels of ethical practice on a day-to-day basis.

The principle is further brought out by the method the industries employ to deal with workers in its facilities. Payne and Landry (2005) explain that workers in the tourism and hospitality industry are encouraged, trained, and developed as a means towards fostering their commitment.

Method

The qualitative method will be used to gather data on the experiences and perceptions of tourists who have visited cultural tourism destinations. This method will involve open-ended interviews with tourists and other stakeholders, such as government officials, tourism operators, and local residents' satisfaction.

The interviews will be conducted in person or through video conferencing platforms such as Zoom and Skype. The purpose of the interviews will be to gain ethics in hospitality, the challenges faced by tourists with when visiting cultural tourism destinations. Questions will be designed to elicit some information about the accessibility features currently available in these destinations, as well as suggestions for improvements that can be made.

The qualitative method will also involve a review of existing policies and regulations related to

Satisfactions. This review will provide insights into the current state of accessibility in these destinations and identify areas where improvements are needed.

Requested skills

Dress code: Each hotel, company has its own dress code, even though it still requires to remind and mention it to new employees, that they must come with classic uniform with ironed clothes and look neat. They supposed to have good hairstyle for both men and women, it has to be knotted for women not to disobey hygiene rules. Not high heels for women, instead to be comfortable to stand, to work,

to walk whole day at work inside the hotel. No beard is allowed for male employees in hotel sphere. Light make up for women and not to wear attractive jewelry and lipsticks.

Hygiene: Each hotel employee must follow hygiene rules of each department. Nails must be cut shortly and nice shaped. Depends on the department to wash their hand after each work for housekeeping, kitchen and F&B departments. To look and smell good. One of the hygiene rule that each hotel employee has to follow. Clean uniform and etc.

Punctuality: Punctuality is the most requested skills from any employee at any company of the world. That is one of the most important impression can be earned by managers and shows loyalty and responsibility of the staff to his work. Coming on time is being responsible, paying attention to details of the rules, obeying managers' tasks and earning his trust.

Responsibility:

If a company hires an employee and finds an employee suitable on specific position. Company has no choice but to trust you, relies on employee's responsibility, punctuality and loyalty. Company will rely on employee's performance. That, employee will be responsible for the whole department, will feel the responsibility and complete the task or serve the customers. After observing and starting the work, to feel the responsibility to be able to serve customers and take their payment details and key in them in the desktop in opera app and record on your own notebook to share details with co-workers and managers for informing them about the situation. At this point, actions must be based on correct motives that ultimately translate into the consideration of treating employees morally and in accordance with ethical requirements according to the argument put forward by Fennel and Malloy (1999).

Loyalty:

Loyalty is being a loyal to your company. While company hires you, they will be

Team player: By imagining a team, a staff shall not an imagine or limit his imagination only with his own department. If he is hired at Front office, it does not mean that, his colleagues at that area and department only his team. His team is consisting of many departments, such as: Kitchen, F&B, Housekeeping, Spa, Security, Finance, Engineering and other department. Whole hotel is considered to be each employees team.

Friendly: Each employee earns more trust and friends by being friends with his surroundings. Employees are not forced to like each other but have to respect each employee, does not matter on which position he works on. Colleagues are supposed to be treated like customers.

Flexible/Adaptable:

By rules any employee has to work eight hours per day. Sometimes it will be out of control at work areas, here is requested for an employee to be a flexible and an adaptable. When is requested to stay extra hours, an employee has to have an understanding of team player role and support the team with a manager, indeed mutual understanding comes from both sides. When an employee also needs some leave, while an employee has to work an eight hours per day, but exception some days his health won't allow him to work eight hours or full week. Those moments mutual understanding plays a role, and managers, supervisors have to support and arrange their employees shuffle timetable to cover that employee who is not able to work one day or couple days.

Positive:

As an employee, staff passes from all type of situations and gains an experience. At the same time an employee has to look at situations positively, each case, will get him gain experience. Remaining calm and looking positive at that case will make an employee more professional.

Effective Strategies in Communication ethics

Hotel industry is a business where, customers are always right. Rather to have a mistake or not. There are some useful tips for an employee to get out of the situation smoothly.

Apologize: There are billions of cases, which will make person force to accept the situation and simply apologize, even though if there was not your fault. To soften the communication and to calm the customer, an employee has to apologize politely and carefully listen to complain. To understand it well before replying or commenting.

Strategize: While customer is complaining, after hearing it carefully and understanding the problem, try to figure it out the solution, making a plan in the head, using strategies by relying on your experiences. As a professional employee, your company is your face, and your co-worker does deserve the same respect, as you respect the guest. Employees cannot blame their colleagues or work place or their own city. (*such as: internet works bad in whole city, that is terrible, or housekeepers are not enough experienced sorry about it, that shows you not professional, in all cases employees should not blame their team, company and city*)

Mobilize:

Relying on his/her experience and knowledge, finding solution on the problem and getting back to the customer and following with the situation. (*Sir, I have found a maintenance engineer and called them to your room, within 5 minutes they will know your room for fixing an air-condition in your room. Sorry that you have faced such problem*)

Personalize:

Personalizing the problem as if it is your own problem, follow up with the case, until the issue is not solved. After solving the issue, kindly ask, (*sir sorry that you have faced such problem, now it is all fixed, Can I help you with anything else today? Have a great day ahead!*)

Analyzing

Analyzing a problem is, as a professional employee, employee has to record everything on his notebook, for sharing information with shift partner and a manager, in case they would know the issue and a solution which is made by an employee. It will also help them to learn the customer and their requests. Which will help any employee to learn the customer's history and to serve better?

Discussion and Conclusion

As a conclusion of article it is an extensive prime conceptual findings, the model of regional innovation systems is considered to be the most adequate for the tourism system, and the ethics as important structures for its operation. Regarding this theoretical approach, a steppingstone for the analysis of hospitality management systems may be developed, allowing a number of theories to be advanced and checked through the analyzed of the results from the empirical part of the thesis.

The results provided enable uncover essential conclusions on the innovative operation of tourism firms and districts, the networking approaches developed due to the innovation processes, the role of regional knowledge and regional specific conditions for tourism innovation and the perception of tourism enterprises regarding the innovation environment and the benefit of the evolution and success of hospitality ethics.

Ethical behavior is one of the most important requested skills in hospitality. It starts from dress codes, ends on mobilized skills from an employee. Any employee since they start their career in hotel industry they have to follow these rules.

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